

TRANSFORMATION OF SLUM-FREE RESIDENTIAL AREAS BASED ON SUSTAINABLE SETTLEMENT IN THE FISHERMAN'S VILLAGE IN MAKASSAR CITY

NASRULLAH¹, RUDY LATIEF², HERMINAWATI³ and HASANUDDIN REMMANG⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Universitas Bosowa.

Email: ¹megah.arististik.@gmail.com, ²rudi.latief@universitasbosowa.ac.id, ³herminawaty82@gmail.com, ⁴remmanghasan@gmail.com

Abstract

The study, entitled "Slum-Free Transformation Based on Sustainable Settlement in Fishing Villages in Makassar City," discusses efforts to organize and improve fishing settlements, which have historically been synonymous with slums, overcrowding, and a lack of basic infrastructure. The transformation was carried out by integrating the concept of sustainable settlement, emphasizing environmental, social, and economic aspects. From an environmental perspective, the development includes improving sanitation, providing clean water, managing waste, managing drainage, and strengthening green open spaces. From a social perspective, community participation and strengthening local institutions are key to maintaining sustainability. Meanwhile, from an economic perspective, improving fishing business facilities, creating hygienic markets, and developing productive businesses are key strategies to improve the welfare of coastal communities. This study focuses on efforts to transform fishing settlements in Makassar City, which have historically been vulnerable to slum-like problems, such as building density, poor sanitation, limited basic infrastructure, and poor environmental quality. The transformation was carried out by adopting the concept of sustainable settlement, which emphasizes three main aspects: (a) Environmental Aspects. (b) Improvement of basic infrastructure such as clean water, sanitation, drainage, and waste management. (c) Arrangement of green open spaces and regional adaptation to climate change, including flood mitigation and marine pollution. The research organization has two aspects, namely: (1) Social Aspects, including: Empowerment of fishing communities through active participation in planning and management of residential environments, Strengthening local institutions so that communities are able to maintain the sustainability of the planned environment. (2) Economic Aspects, including: Provision of supporting facilities for fishing activities, such as hygienic fish markets, seafood processing facilities, and productive business spaces, and Increasing economic access through empowerment programs and support for small businesses based on coastal resources. The research results show that the transformation of slum settlements into sustainable fishing settlements requires integration between government policies, community participation, and the implementation of environmentally friendly and inclusive spatial design. Thus, coastal fishing areas will not only be free from the impression of slums, but also develop into livable, productive, and sustainable environments.

Keywords: Settlements, Slums, Sustainable, Settlements, Environmentally Friendly.

INTRODUCTION

Makassar City, as a coastal city and center of economic growth in Eastern Indonesia, boasts a sizable fishing village. However, this area still faces numerous slum settlements characterized by uninhabitable housing conditions, high building density, poor sanitation, limited access to clean water, and inadequate waste and drainage management. This situation directly impacts the quality of life of the fishing community, most of whom are in the lower-middle economic class. In addition to physical settlement issues, fishing communities also face social and

economic challenges, such as limited access to education, low competitiveness, and dependence on unstable fishing activities. This places fishing communities in a cycle of structural poverty that is difficult to break without planned transformation efforts. The following image shows the Tallo (Ujung Tanah) slum area of Makassar City.

Figure 1: Condition of Coastal Settlements in Slum Areas-2025

As urban development demands increase, coastal slum areas have the potential to become increasingly marginalized if not addressed seriously. Therefore, a settlement transformation concept is needed that not only organizes the physical environment to free it from slums but also integrates the principles of sustainable settlement. This concept emphasizes three main aspects:

Makassar City, as a coastal city and center of economic growth in Eastern Indonesia, has a fairly extensive fishing village area that plays a vital role in providing fishery resources. However, this area still faces numerous slum settlement issues characterized by uninhabitable housing, high building density, poor sanitation, limited access to clean water, and inadequate waste and drainage management.

These conditions directly impact the quality of life of fishing communities, most of whom live under economic constraints.² Baud-Bovy, and Lawson. (2018) [2]. In addition to physical settlement issues, fishing communities also face social and economic constraints, such as poor access to education, limited alternative employment opportunities, and dependence on uncertain catches. This creates a cycle of structural poverty that is difficult to break without appropriate development interventions. On the other hand, the coastal fishing areas of Makassar City have enormous potential for development, including: (1) Abundant fishery

resources as a basis for strengthening the local economy. (2) Potential for the creative economy and marine tourism, due to its strategic location, close to the city center and sea trade routes, thus attracting tourists and investors. (3) Socio-cultural potential, where fishing communities possess local wisdom, maritime traditions, and strong community ties, which can serve as social capital for sustainable development. (4) Potential for improving environmental quality, where slum-free areas can become models for modern coastal settlements that maintain environmental sustainability and support climate resilience.

Therefore, a transformation of fishing village areas based on sustainable settlements is needed that not only addresses slum issues but also optimizes the potential of coastal, social, and cultural resources within fishing communities. With this strategy, the coastal areas of Makassar City can develop into livable, economically productive, socially inclusive, and environmentally friendly settlements.

Analysis of the settlement situation of the coastal fishing village area in Makassar City: (a) Social conditions, namely: (i) High population density in coastal areas, especially in traditional fishing village areas. (ii) The level of education is relatively low, most people only complete basic education, thus affecting access to employment. (iii) Public health remains a challenge, with poor sanitation, limited access to clean water, and the risk of infectious diseases. (iv) Local wisdom is still strong, for example solidarity between residents, mutual cooperation, and the Bugis-Makassar maritime culture. (b) Economic conditions, namely; (i) Main livelihoods: fishermen, fish/seaweed farmers, dock workers, small traders, and informal workers in the coastal tourism sector. (ii) Income is unstable because it depends on the season, fish prices, and weather factors. (iii) High economic vulnerability, especially during the lean season (west winds/big waves) which prevent fishermen from going to sea. (iv) Low economic diversification, mostly dependent on the fisheries sector without alternative businesses. Nany Yuliasuti. (2012.).[7]

From an economic perspective, the transformation of the area aims to lift fishermen from economic vulnerability due to limited market access, low catch value, and a lack of productive business facilities. Through more organized area planning, the development of supporting infrastructure such as hygienic fish markets, seafood processing centers, and small business spaces is expected to increase fishermen's incomes. Furthermore, community economic empowerment is carried out by providing access to training, empowering micro-enterprises, and integrating the fisheries sector with marine tourism and the creative economy.

Opportunities for Developing Potential Coastal Ecotourism and Marine Tourism at Losari Beach, Samalona Island, and Barrang Lompo Island. Downstream fishery product processing (processing of fish, seaweed, crab, etc.). Digitalization of marine product marketing to increase fishermen's incomes. Government and NGO programs for structuring fishing villages and building the capacity of coastal communities. In general, coastal communities in Makassar City face vulnerable socio-economic conditions, posed by environmental challenges and limited infrastructure. However, they have significant potential in the fisheries sector, maritime culture, and marine tourism development if supported by appropriate policies and sustainable empowerment.

On the other hand, the coastal fishing areas of Makassar City have significant potential for development, including:

1. Abundant fishery resources that can serve as the foundation for strengthening the local economy.
2. Creative economy and marine tourism potential, given the strategic location close to the city center and major sea trade routes, which can attract both tourists and investors.
3. Socio-cultural potential, as the fishing communities possess local wisdom, maritime traditions, and strong community ties that can serve as social capital for sustainable development.
4. Opportunities for improving environmental quality, where well-organized, slum-free areas can become models of modern coastal settlements that preserve environmental sustainability and support climate resilience.

Therefore, a transformation of fishing village areas based on sustainable settlements is needed that not only addresses slum issues but also optimizes the potential of coastal resources, social development, and cultural well-being of fishing communities. With this strategy, Makassar City's coastal areas can develop into livable, economically productive, socially inclusive, and environmentally friendly settlements.

METHODS

1) Research Approach

This study employs a qualitative-descriptive approach to explore the existing conditions, challenges, and potential of fishing villages in depth. The qualitative-descriptive approach emphasizes a thorough understanding of phenomena based on real conditions in the field rather than statistical data. It is termed *descriptive* because its aim is to portray and present facts, situations, and social realities as they are, which are then interpreted by the researcher.

2) Research Location

The research was conducted through fieldwork involving direct observation of the living conditions in coastal fishing settlements in Makassar City. A case study approach was adopted, focusing on several representative fishing villages (such as Ujung Tanah, Tallo, Untia, and others) in Makassar City.

3) Types and Sources of Data

- a) Primary data: Collected through in-depth interviews with community members, fishing leaders, and local government officials; observation of physical settlement conditions (housing, sanitation, access to clean water, roads, and drainage); and questionnaires on the socio-economic conditions of the community.
- b) Secondary data: Obtained from Statistics Indonesia (BPS), the Makassar City Spatial Plan (RTRW), data on slum areas from the Housing and Settlement Agency, as well as policy documents and regulations related to housing and coastal areas.

4) Data Collection Techniques

- a) **Field observation:** to document the physical conditions of slum areas.
- b) **In-depth interviews:** conducted with residents, neighborhood leaders (RT/RW), traditional leaders, and government officials.
- c) **Focus group discussions (FGDs):** to explore community-based aspirations and solutions for area transformation.
- d) **Questionnaires/surveys:** to collect quantitative data on income, population density, and infrastructure needs, as well as documentation such as photos, maps, satellite imagery, and official government records.

5) Data Analysis Methods

- a) **Qualitative descriptive analysis:** to explain the social, economic, cultural, and environmental conditions.
- b) **Spatial analysis:** using maps or GIS to map the distribution of slum areas and potential transformation.
- c) **SWOT analysis:** to identify the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats of area transformation.
- d) **Thematic analysis:** to categorize interview and FGD findings into themes (e.g., infrastructure needs, local culture, community participation).

6) Research Stages

- a) **Preliminary study:** literature review and identification of targeted areas.
- b) **Field survey and data collection:** observation, interviews, and questionnaires.
- c) **Analysis of existing conditions:** covering social, economic, environmental, and spatial aspects.
- d) **Needs and problem analysis:** identifying the factors causing slum conditions.
- e) **Design of transformation model:** developing a sustainable settlement concept based on community participation.

7) Research Outputs

- a) **Profile of the existing conditions of fishing communities:** slum area maps, socio-economic data, and environmental potential.
- b) **Identification of factors causing slum conditions in coastal areas.**
- c) **Conceptual model for the transformation of fishing settlements based on sustainable settlement principles.**
- d) **Policy recommendations for the Makassar City Government regarding the improvement of coastal settlements.**

RESEARCH RESULTS

Determining the final concept of this research requires the analyzed factors to be reviewed against the established criteria, namely Sustainable Settlements. To determine the factors from the analyzed criteria and the criteria in accordance with the Sustainable Settlements reference, both will be analyzed to form a single criterion using qualitative descriptive analysis with data validation through a group discussion forum.

The principles of the Sustainable Settlements concept are:

- (a) Physical spatial transformation.
- (b) Provision of adequate infrastructure and lifecycle management.
- (c) Functional, responsive, and innovative design.
- (d) Easy and close access to services and facilities.
- (e) Affordable urban living, with city life accessible in every settlement.
- (f) Financial sustainability.

This approach aims to obtain maximum and in-depth results with the agreement of the village stakeholders who participated in the study, in accordance with the research objective, namely to produce a formulation of criteria for improving fishing villages to become slum-free. Formulation of Criteria for the Sustainable Settlement Concept in Research The criteria or principles of the Sustainable Settlements framework were first presented to the informants in a group interview to gather the opinions and agreement of stakeholders and representatives of fishing village residents regarding the points of improvement for the fishing village in the case study. The following is a description and results of the interviews based on the principles of the criteria in the Sustainable Settlements concept.

a. Physical Spatial Transformation

Changes in the spatial and physical form of residential buildings lead to better designs and are more livable. Settlement improvements require physical spatial transformation to make the settlement more habitable. Improving fishing settlements to free them from slums involves improvements in the form of spatial transformation or changes to the physical and spatial aspects of the fishing settlement. Spatial transformation itself can be implemented in fishing settlements by improving empty spaces that are not yet utilized by the local community. It can be utilized as a valuable space, such as a communal space for drying fish or other activities, such as smoking fish, that can attract local residents. This can increase local income. Improvements to the fishing village in the case study include repairs to the main gate of the village in Mariso District, Makassar City. The physical condition of the fish auction facility (TPI) owned by local residents, which is in poor condition, can be improved. These improvements can be proposed to the local government and implemented through the collaborative efforts of the fishing village residents. It is hoped that after the spatial transformation of the fishing village, it can become an even better village, free from slums and sustainable.

The following figure shows the physical condition of a habitable house.

Figure 2: Type 1 habitable house for fishermen in Makassar City.2025

b. Provision of adequate infrastructure and lifecycle management

Provision of infrastructure supporting a decent settlement and having adequate management of the settlement. The Tambak Mariso settlement lacks adequate infrastructure and good environmental management. This is evident in the physical condition of the settlement and the existing environment. A sustainable settlement must be supported by adequate infrastructure and good environmental management.

Infrastructure already exists and is available in the case study. The physical condition of infrastructure such as roads, bridges, and gates, although minimal, still functions quite well. However, these require renewal and repair to improve the physical condition of the village and maintain it. Regular maintenance is also necessary to manage the environment and the repaired infrastructure to ensure its continued condition and become a sustainable village.

c. Functional, responsive, and innovative design

Having a functional, responsive, and innovative design to meet future needs. Having a settlement design that is functionally integrated and responsive to existing potential and has an innovative design. Improving the sustainable settlement environment. This can be seen in terms of function, responsiveness, and design, both in terms of space requirements and the settlement design. If these criteria are met, a city can be considered sustainable.

The existing conditions at the study location, namely Tambak Mariso village, have functional settlement conditions but lack responsive and innovative designs. This is evident from the

buildings and surrounding settlements, which require design improvements. This includes the design of the residents' houses in the settlement (Dahuri, R., et al., 2001) [5] and also the design of the fishermen's settlement itself. The design should respond to the function of the houses in the fishing village.

A design that can accommodate the activities of the residents of the Mariso and Tallo fishing villages is needed so that this Melayan village has an attractive design and can attract the attention of local residents. The residential design of this fishing village is also very much needed because this village has a distinctive feature as a fishing village that provides and sells various catches from the sea and from the ponds produced by local residents.

However, it is very unfortunate because the Tambak Cemandi fishing village does not yet have a good design, which is responsive and lacks functionality. Therefore, based on the principles of the Sustainable Settlement criteria, the arrangement and design of the fishing settlement is needed so that the fishing village becomes a developed and sustainable village.

The following figure 3. Innovative fisherman's house concept

Figure 3: Type 2. Habitable houses for fishermen in Makassar City. 2025

d. Easy and close access to services and facilities.

Having clear and accessible access and access to the services and facilities available in each settlement. The accessibility system for people from one place to another is also a crucial factor in building a sustainable urban environment. The availability of public spaces or urban green spaces that are safe and inclusive for the community is also essential. A city has a path element, meaning roads or access that facilitates community gathering in a particular location within the city.

Within a residential area, a residential area has roads from village alleys to parks, fields, or other places that can be used by local residents to socialize with one another and enjoy the fresh, green air free from pollution and so on. If these criteria are met, a city can be considered sustainable.

This is because the fishing village in the case study has public spaces such as mangrove areas, fishing boat mooring areas, and fishpond edges. In these places, the local community socializes, exchanges information, and engages in other social activities.

Easy access to the road from the alleys of the fishermen's settlements to these green open space spots is quite clear. However, it is unfortunate that the condition of the roads in the fishing village still needs improvement, related to the roads that have not been paved and are still made of soil that is hardened with gravel and shell waste from this village, which is used daily by residents who live in this village.

However, it must be noted here, the fishing village in Mariso District and the tip of Tallo/Untia land requires improvement in the condition of the road that is access to public spaces and green spaces in the village area, because the village is located very far from the edge and close to the sea. Figure 4. Type of residential house with easy access.

Figure 4: The concept of a slum-free, easily accessible residential home

e. Concept for youth facilities, such as a studio or reading room. The innovative design is functional, responsive, and innovative

The concept of utilizing the pond area as a public facility, namely a floating gazebo. The floating gazebo can be used by all residents and youth to develop their creativity, with a design concept like that shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Concept of public facilities

The analysis above elucidates the concept of Sustainable Settlement, correlated with the first research objective, namely the analysis of factors causing slums based on slum criteria and existing conditions. However, addressing the slum problem in this fishing settlement requires steps or priorities for action. The correlation that needs to be understood relates to the condition of the human resources or residents of the fishing settlement in the case study. The analysis in the previous chapter discussed the influence of the social and economic characteristics of the fishing settlement community on slums in the residential environment. The results of this analysis serve as a reference in developing steps or priorities for action to address slums in the fishing settlement, which have been adapted to the principles of Sustainable Settlements. The

stages or priorities for taking action to address slums in fishing settlements, adapted to the Sustainable Settlement approach, which can be applied according to the characteristics of the community in the fishing settlement area, are explained in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Priority Stages in the Concept of Slum-Free Fishing Settlements with the Sustainable Settlement Concept

Stages of Settlement Improvement

Priority Stage	Concept	Description
Understanding residents' perceptions of the improvement concept	Residents' perceptions of the slum-free village program	The initial stage to build awareness, explore community perspectives, and guide local residents on the importance of improving settlement quality.
	Improving social quality	Strengthening social capacity and community participation to support sustainable settlement transformation.
	Improving community economy	Addressing slum conditions through economic empowerment initiatives within fishing communities.
Data collection and legal verification of residents	Population density in fishing settlements	Conducted to prevent errors prior to settlement upgrading by ensuring accurate demographic and occupancy data.
	Land ownership in fishing settlements	Verification of land tenure to provide legal certainty before housing and infrastructure improvements.
Housing improvement for local residents	Characteristics of fishing settlement buildings	The core stage, focusing on upgrading substandard housing in accordance with standards and residents' needs.
	Physical condition of settlement housing	Ensuring houses are rehabilitated to meet livable housing requirements.
	Innovative, functional, and responsive design	Promoting housing designs that are adaptable to residents' social and environmental contexts.
Improvement of public facilities in slum areas	Accessibility and service coverage	The next core stage after housing improvement, aimed at upgrading community facilities to meet sustainable settlement standards.
	Road accessibility	Providing proper road networks to improve mobility and connectivity.
	Drainage systems	Ensuring adequate drainage to prevent flooding and improve sanitation.
	Solid waste management	Establishing proper waste management to maintain environmental health.
	Fire safety measures	Introducing fire protection and prevention systems in settlements.
	Safe and affordable housing	Ensuring housing improvements align with safety, affordability, and inclusivity.
	Provision of adequate infrastructure and life-cycle management	Developing sustainable infrastructure with proper maintenance systems.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the final analysis in this study is to formulate a concept for developing a slum-free fishing settlement area using the Sustainable Settlement concept. The final analysis in this study establishes stages or priorities for action to address slums in fishing settlements, adapted to the Sustainable Settlement principles described in the table in the previous chapter. The second objective of this study is to examine the relationship between social and economic conditions in the community and their impact on slums in fishing settlements. By gathering information from various sources representing each community group, the fishermen's settlements were categorized based on their social and economic conditions, resulting in three key points that serve as criteria for a slum-free fishing settlement concept. The following concept was developed regarding the social and economic conditions of the community:

1. Improving the Community's Social Quality. The analysis shows that the better or more integrated social quality of a community will impact their behavior in carrying out all activities, including protecting their living environment.
2. Improving the quality of the community's economy. Analyzing the willingness of residents in the fishing village used as a case study to improve environmental quality indirectly impacts the residents' economy. Residents with higher incomes also demonstrate a greater awareness and willingness to care for the environment around their settlements. This serves as a basis for a village improvement program that should also boost the village's economy, enabling them to become more independent and better understand the importance of maintaining a slum-free environment. The results of the first research and the analysis of the second research objective serve as a reference in developing the concept of
2. The concept of a habitable fishing house. This sketch outlines a concept for a habitable fishing house that meets standards by separating the commercial and private areas. Therefore, the storage or sale of marine catches. Understanding sustainable maintenance of slum-free settlements. This stage is the final stage after repairing slum houses and public facilities. Of course, an understanding of maintenance is needed to create a sustainable slum-free village in accordance with the standards and concepts of Sustainable Settlement and can be carried out by local residents.

Recommendations

- 1) Regional governments need to develop specific policies and regulations that support environmentally sustainable development of fishing areas.
- 2) The participation of fishing communities must be strengthened through education programs, training, and the establishment of solid local institutions to ensure sustainable transformation.
- 3) Environmentally friendly infrastructure such as waste management systems, adaptive drainage, and renewable energy should be prioritized in regional development.
- 4) Integrating the fishing economy with the marine tourism sector, seafood processing, and modern markets can improve welfare while preserving coastal cultural identity.

Bibliography

- 1) A'yun, Qurrotul. 2016. *Evaluasi Tingkat Kualitas Hidup dengan Kriteria Eco-Settlement pada Permukiman Nelayan di Desa Pesisir Tambak Wedi*. EMARA Indonesian Journal of Architecture. Surabaya.
- 2) Baud-Bovy, M., & Lawson. 2018. *Tourism and Recreation Handbook of Planning and Design*. London: Architectural Press.
- 3) Carr, Stephen. 1992. *Public Space*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- 4) Christiawan, Putu Indra, & I Gede Budiarta. 2017. *Entitas Permukiman Kumuh di Wilayah Pesisir*. Singaraja: Universitas Pendidikan Ganesha.
- 5) Dahuri, R., et al. 2001. *Pengelolaan Sumber Daya Wilayah Pesisir dan Lautan Secara Terpadu*. Bogor: Pradnya Paramita.
- 6) Darmawan, E. 2009. *Ruang Publik dalam Arsitektur Kota*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit UNDIP.
- 7) Dimitra, Sonya, & Nany Yuliasuti. 2012. *Potensi Kampung Nelayan sebagai Modal Permukiman Berkelanjutan di Tambaklorok, Kelurahan Tanjung Mas*. Semarang: Jurnal Teknik PWK, Volume 1.
- 8) Fachrudin, Hilma Tamiami. 2019. *Penataan Kampung Nelayan dengan Pendekatan Arsitektur Ekologi di Kelurahan Bagan Deli Kota Medan*.
- 9) Groat, L., & Wang, D. 2013. *Architectural Research Methods* (2nd ed.). Canada, USA: John Wiley and Sons Inc.
- 10) Hajrah, Andi. 2016. *Pengelolaan Sumberdaya Pesisir yang Berkelanjutan bagi Pengembangan Kawasan Pesisir di Kecamatan Galesong Selatan Kabupaten Takalar*. Makassar: UIN Alauddin Makassar.
- 11) Haryadi, & Setiawan, B. 1995. *Arsitektur Lingkungan dan Perilaku*. Jakarta: PPPSL Dirjen Dikti Depdikbud.
- 12) Prasti, Annisa, & Widyastuti. 2015. *Kondisi Fisik dan Kualitas Permukiman Kawasan Pesisir Kecamatan Baolan Kabupaten Tolitoli*. Tadaluko: Jurnal Ilmiah Untad, Vol. 3.
- 13) Rahardjo, Priyanto. 2002. *Nelayan Nusantara: Sebuah Filsafah Kehidupan*.
- 14) Rapoport, Amos. 2017. *Human Aspects of Urban Form: Towards a Man-Environmental Approach to Urban Form and Design*. New York: Pergamon Press.